

Creating value through the use of legumes seminar, 17.3.2020

Description

Grain legumes are paving the way for innovative legume-based food products and feeding solutions. However, there are several issues related to scaling-up the value creating potential of grain legumes in Europe.

This seminar is about exploring the prospects and challenges of creating value through grain legumes. During the first half of the day, international guests from Germany, Sweden, Denmark and Austria will present examples and insights on improving and expanding the use of legumes for food and feed in Europe. The second half of the day starts with considerations about the role of legumes in the Planetary Health Diet and to what extent it can be applied in Finland.

The seminar is organized by: Ground for Growth, as part of Translating knowledge for legume-based farming for feed and food systems (Legumes Translated); Legumes for Sustainable Food System and Healthy Life (Leg4life); and Climate change mitigation and adaptation in Finnish agriculture -coordination project (VILLE). The seminar is supported by Jalofoods.

Place: Technopolis Ruoholahti I

Address: Hiilikatu 3, 00180, Helsinki, Finland

Follow this [link](#) for directions.

Registration

Registration is open until 10.3. Please note, that due to the limited amount of places in the venue, first 90 guests will get a place. Please use the link below to register for this event:

<https://elomake.helsinki.fi/lomakkeet/103605/lomake.html>

Unable to attend in person?

We are also pleased to inform you that the seminar will be recorded and streamed online. Instructions for connecting to the livestream will be sent to all registered participants before the meeting.

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Program

	Presenter	Topic
08:30		Coffee
09:00 - 09:15	Kristina Lindström , University of Helsinki	Welcome speech
09:15 - 10:00	Ulrich Quendt , Landesbetrieb Landwirtschaft Hessen, Germany	Demonstration and knowledge transfer network for expanding and improving cultivation and utilisation for field peas and beans in Germany
10:00 - 10:30	Leopold Rittler , Donau Soja, Austria	Soya from Europe – A Sustainable, Safe and European protein supply
10:30 - 11:15	Karen Hamann , Institute for Food Studies & Agroindustrial Development, Denmark	The diversity of business cases and opportunities for grain legumes in food
11:15 - 12.15	Casimir Schauman , University of Helsinki Karoliina Rimhanen , Natural Resources Institute Finland Marjukka Lamminen , University of Helsinki	Workshop 1 (45 min.): Harnessing the value creation potential from Finnish legumes
12:15 - 13:15	Lunch at restaurant Hiili (at own expense)	
13:15 - 13:45	Anne Maria Pajari , University of Helsinki	The role of legumes in the Planetary Health Diet
13:45 - 14:15	Nicolas Carton , Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Swedish	Grain legumes for the transition towards more sustainable diets – a Swedish perspective
14:15 - 15:15	Casimir Schauman , Karoliina Rimhanen, Marjukka Lamminen	Workshop 2 (45 min.): What does the Planetary Health Diet entail for Finland?
15:15 - 16:15	All invited speakers	Panel discussion with international guests, moderated by Fred Stoddard from the University of Helsinki

Legumes Translated (Translating knowledge for legume-based farming for feed and food systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817634

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Presentation of speakers

Ulrich Quendt is coordinating a knowledge transfer network consisting of 60 conventional as well as organic farms growing field peas or field beans. This network (DemoNetErBo) aims to expand and enhance the cultivation as well as the sustainable use of field peas and field beans. It also focuses on improving the value gained by farmers when growing peas and beans. Special focus is therefore on the development and presentation of legume value chains for feed and food production spanning all levels from breeding to cultivation, processing until consumer use.

Karen Hamann is the CEO and Head of research at the Institute for Food Studies IFAU in Denmark. She holds a Masters' Degree in Agriculture in Copenhagen and has more than 20 years of experience in applied research about global agro-food supply chains. The focus of Karen's work is on markets, supply chains, innovation and business development. She is a partner in the EU-funded project "Transition Paths to Sustainable Legume-based Systems in Europe - TRUE" where she is heading the research about food and feed supply chains and market development opportunities (www.true-project.eu).

Nicolas Carton is an agronomist with enthusiasm for diversification of cropping systems. Nicolas is representing the Swedish project New Legumes Foods, which develops the use of domestic legumes for food (e.g. beans, lentils, peas) to increase the food system sustainability and stimulate a growing bio-economy based on novel, attractive and health-promoting foods.

Leopold Rittler is an agronomist with broad experience in managing natural resources. He is Head of Research and Innovation in Donau Soja and serves as Secretary to the Donau Soja Scientific Advisory Board. Donau Soja is a non-profit membership-based organisation headquartered in Vienna and founded in 2012. Its mission is to support its partners and members in progressing change to address social, environmental and economic challenges in soya production and consumption in Europe.